

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF TEDURAY ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS ON MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

English language learning is a complex phenomenon and challenging that is set of words, grammar, structure, unpredictable spelling, and complexity of organizational ideas. Learning the English language is pivotal to the development of the learners in all aspect. Thus, the classroom is the ideal platform to acquire and learning the English language with the assistance of English teachers. The COVID-19 Pandemic brought distraction to all educational system where the modular distance learning modality is being adopted while learners accustomed to face to face learning approach. This qualitative phenomenological study aimed to explore the lived experiences of selected Teduray English language learners during the modular distance learning from Datu Blah Sinsuat, District of Maguindanao-II, Division. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the participants relevant to the research study. The in-depth interview employing semi-structure research questionnaire was utilized to explicate the challenges and experiences in the phenomena. The Collaizi's, (1978) seven steps strategy in phenomenological approach was utilized to provide rigorous analysis of data. Thus, the findings of the study revealed important themes. Poor Reading Comprehension, Very Poor in Writing, Difficulty in Word Recognition, Poor Writing Skills. Consequently, the coping mechanism of Teduray English language learners were, Studying the Lesson, Asking Assistance from Parents/Siblings. Therefore, the suggested solution of the English

language teachers to the Teduray learners were, Enrichment Activities in Reading and Writing on Module, Learning Through Social Media Platform, Guidance and Supervision from Adults/Parents and lastly, Utilization of Dictionary. The study concluded that, Teduray English language learners had experienced serious difficult challenges in their learning English language on modular distance learning.

Keywords: *English language learning, lived experiences, modular distance learning, Teduray, phenomenology*

INTRODUCTION

Education has a significant impact on the lives of learners. Teachers are one of the most important tools in delivering high-quality education. The introduction of COVID-19 in the Philippines resulted in significant changes in the educational landscape. One of these is the Department of Education's implementation of a new form of instruction. Most education systems have been forced to adopt alternatives to face-to-face teaching and learning as a result of the present COVID-19 dilemma. Many educational systems have transferred activities online in order to continue teaching despite school closures (OECD, 2020). The transition in school teaching-learning delivery to modular distance learning made the delivery of fundamental quality education more difficult for school workers. As stated by Bagood (2020), DepEd authorities are continually looking for methods to overcome difficulties and capacitate teachers and school administrators to become more effective in the field of modular distant learning (Castroverde & Acala, 2021). The majority of students are modular (print) learners, especially in rural locations where internet access is not always available. They are learning at home with the assistance of their parents or guardians, who have taken on the role of teachers. Teachers, on the other hand, provide guidance to the parents. Teaching their children at home, particularly the younger ones from kindergarten to grade three. The same is true in Grades 4 to 6, albeit with less direction than in the early grades, when students receive more attention and monitoring. The modular system had certain difficulties, particularly in engaging students who were uninterested in studying (J. A. Barcenas and M. B. Bibon, 2021). Students also complained about too many activities in class. As they indicated, a teacher would assign them nearly three exercises in a subject, leaving them with less time to carefully answer all of them. Sundarasen et al. validated the difficulty of remote learning in their investigation (2020).

Some Malaysian university students voiced concern about the enormous number of assignments assigned by their professors. Their studies also demonstrated that this difficulty had a significant impact on the students' stress and anxiety levels. Sarvestani et al., (2019) have a similar situation, in which students complain about the huge volume and quantity of courses that they must complete. More learners think they didn't fully comprehend the modules. They even have trouble understanding the lessons when they are taught face to face (Helpline, 2020). As a result, it is clear that there are issues with using modular distance learning (Castroverde & Acala, 2021).

Therefore, a poor learning environment makes it difficult for students to participate in remote learning comfortably. Students' comments have repeatedly highlighted this issue. Creating a happy and supportive learning environment has always been a challenge in remote education, particularly for most disadvantaged families (Baticulon et al., 2020).

There are also parents who do not know how to read and write, making it more difficult to teach their children the lessons in their subject areas. This deficiency of learning the English language on Modular Distance Learning is very much observable in one of the rural schools in Maguindanao II especially at Resa Elementary School, Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School. Engaging in the teaching and learning process using the English language is a serious concern for the school and to its educators. In this context, this study was conducted to describe and understand the live experiences of grade 4 Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning as affected by the factors which hamper their learning and ability to use English as an important component in their academic endeavor. This made the study relevant and timely.

Research Questions

This study determined the lived experiences of Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning at Resa Elementary School, Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the challenges encountered by Grade 4 Teduray English language learners on modular distance learning in the following:
 - 1.1 reading; and
 - 1.2 writing?
2. What are the coping mechanisms of Grade 4 Teduray English language learners in overcoming the challenges on modular distance learning in the following:
 - 2.1 reading; and
 - 2.2 writing?
3. What are the suggested solutions of the English Language Teachers in the following language parameters:
 - 3.1 reading; and
 - 3.2 writing?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the method employed in this qualitative research. This includes the research design used, research participants, the data collection, locale of the study, the research instruments, ethical consideration, and the data gathering procedures.

Research Design

The researchers used a qualitative design employing phenomenology in order to generate the interpretation of the text relating to the shared experiences of selected Teduray English language learners in the course of modular approach to learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Phenomenology, as defined by Creswell (2013). As cited by Pulindao & Mohamad, (2023). In addition, qualitative research commonly produces a meaningful and detailed information about much smaller number of people and cases (Patton, 1990). that talks about the study of things in their natural setting (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011) as cited in Fukofuka ,2014; Mohamad, 2022; Manakan, Untong, Mohamad, & Sinsuat, 2023; Zaniel, Mohamad & Parcon, 2023; Ugalingan,. et al., 2023; Pulindao & Mohamad, 2023)

The Phenomenological approach was used to describe how one orients to live experiences (Sloan & Bowe, 2014). as cited by, Pulindao and Mohamad, (2023). Phenomenology allows the researchers to get in deep conversation with the participants in order to invite readers to understand the participants' lived experiences through the texts disclosed in front of them. In order to collect the necessary data needed for the understanding aimed to determine the lived experiences of Teduray English language learners on Modular Distance Learning. The participants were asked on the challenges encountered by Grade 4 Teduray English language learners on modular distance learning in the following language parameters: a.) reading; and b.) writing, the coping mechanisms of Grade 4 Teduray English language learners in overcoming the challenges on modular distance learning in the following language parameters: a.) reading; and b.) writing, the suggested solutions of the Teduray learners in learning the English language in the following language parameters. This study focused on the description of the participants' lived experiences which relate to the phenomenon. Cresswell (2007) summaries the philosophical postulation associated with phenomenology as the study of the life experiences of individuals, with the understanding that these experiences are conscious ones. The study includes the development of descriptions of the substances of these experiences, not explanations or analyses.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Resa Elementary School, Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School. Resa Elementary School is situated in Resa, Datu Blah Sinsuat, Maguindanao. It is approximately 46.1 km away from Cotabato City and 41.7 km away from Datu Odin Sinsuat Maguindanao. It is located at Barangay Resa in the municipality of Datu Blah Sinsuat in the province of Maguindanao. The 2015 Census determined that barangay Resa have 2,007 total of population. This represented 8.02% of the total population of Datu Blah T. Sinsuat municipality. On January 1950, Resa Elementary School was established at Sitio Kamis in barangay Resa. Due to the conflict happened in the year 2017 which resulted to the transfer of residents to other barangays, the school was also relocated at Sitio Padian of the same barangay. It was situated at 700sq land with five buildings consisting eight classrooms and one multifunction room of the former Resa National High School where the said school was originated. Since the

said school was also transferred to other barangays in Datu Blah Sinsuat, the buildings were given to the Resa elementary school with the pursuant of the land owner Datu Gimmie Sinsuat on his pure intention of education continuity to the people of barangay Resa. Resa Elementary School was re-established with the guidance of Ms. Marivic Solmerano Ariston, the current School Head of Sedem Elementary school who also acted as the school head of Resa Elementary School as well as Meti Primary School. Currently, the school is handled by its two permanent teachers headed by Hasma U. Butukan as Teacher in-Charge with the guidance of the District Supervisor Miss Samira S. Mustapha. On the other hand, Kinimi Elementary School is situated in Kinimi, Datu Blah Sinsuat, Maguindanao. It is approximately 38.8 km away from Cotabato City and 54.4 km away from Datu Odin Sinsuat Maguindanao. Kinimi Elementary School is demographically situated in Kinimi, one of the barangays in the municipality of Datu Blah T. Sinsuat in the province of Maguindanao. Kinimi Elementary School was tested again when flood hits, which resulted to devastation. The same of what was happened before the Kinimi Elementary School was rebuilt in the service of the people and its stakeholders with the utmost leadership of Mrs. Milaida T. Utto as a school principal. Meanwhile, the Nalkan Elementary School is situated in Nalkan, Datu Blah Sinsuat, Maguindanao. It is approximately 36.3 km away from Cotabato City and 36.9 km away from Datu Odin Sinsuat Maguindanao. Currently, the school is handled by its seven permanent teachers headed by Sampaguita S. Casada as School Principal with the guidance of the District Supervisor Miss Samira S. Mustapha.

Participants of the study

The participants of the study were seven (7) and three (3) English language teachers from Resa Elementary School, Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School. These Teduray English Language Learners were officially enrolled during the school year 2021-2022.

The learner-participants were purposively chosen since they were Teduray English Language Learners from Grade 4 who are sincerely and willingly participated in the data gathering. The consent of their parents were secured. The teacher-participants were selected since they were the only English language teachers at the said schools.

Research Instrument

This study used a semi-structured interview guide questionnaire. This was verified and checked by thesis adviser and the panel members. The instrument contained an open-ended questions with three parts to gather information about the lived experiences of Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning. The first question talked about the challenges in English Language Learning on Modular Distance Learning, second was their coping mechanisms in overcoming the challenges in English Language Learning on Modular Distance Learning, and the third was the suggested solutions of English language teachers to help address the challenges of Teduray English Language Learners in Modular Distance Learning. In this study, each interview started with acclimatization to prepare the participant psychologically and emotionally as the purpose

of the interview was slowly unfolded to them without necessarily being told. Since the participants understood Filipino language, the interviewers anticipate the possibility of asking questions in Filipino. Thus, the questions were framed in English but there was a ready translation in Filipino in the event the researcher sensed the need to use the translated version. Moreover, this was done to ensure that the questions are well-understood in order to obtain rich substantial data. A semi-structured set of questions were arranged to steer and guide the interview as well as to avoid leading questions as suggested by Morse and Richards (2002) (as cited in Kalis, 2018). A semi-structured interview guide is a technique for generating qualitative data and is characterized by open-ended questions rather than closed type to allow free flowing of thoughts from the participant. The interviewer is free to probe interesting areas that arise from participant's interest or concerns (Lindolf & Taylor, 2002) as cited in Kalis (2018).

To assess whether an instrument is valid, different sources of evidence could be evaluated such as content validity evidence. As cited by Samson (2017), (as cited in Kalis, 2018), Beck and Gable (2001), content validity stresses "the degree to which items in an instrument adequately represent the domain of content". Moreover, they state that content validity should be assessed in the developmental phase of the instrument rather than evaluating its final form.

Data Gathering Procedures

The following procedures were carefully followed during the conduct of the study: Transmittal letter was sent to the District Supervisor of Datu Blah Sinsuat District asking for her approval for the conduct of the study and to the Principal of Kinimi Elementary School and Nalkan Elementary School. A letter was sent also to the class adviser of Grade 4-A of Resa Elementary School, and Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School and discuss the subject of the study. A letter of consent was sent to the guardian of the participants to ask permission and fully aware them about the study. Upon the approval, the researchers scheduled an in-depth interview with the participants. The in-depth-interview was scheduled at the most convenient time of the participants with their guardian/s at their respective schools. The in-depth-interview was conducted with the participant. They were invited at the school together with their guardian for the one on one interview which lasted for 20 minutes. Interview instruments and other materials was made ready for the use of the researchers. After the in-depth-interview, the researcher carefully transcribed the data gathered verbatim and systematically. The transcribing of data gathered was rechecked by listening to the recorded audio multiple times. This is to ensure the clarity and correctness of transcribing the information given by the participants. In order to validate this study, it was presented to the experts from Mindanao State University-Maguindanao.

Data Analysis

The researchers utilized the Collaizi's, (1978) seven steps strategy in data analysis in phenomenological approach that provided a rigorous and intensive analysis. (Mohamad, 2022). According to Collaizi, stated that, to understand, describe, depict and the lived

experiences of Teduray English language learners during the modular distance learning brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic. The main objective employing this method is generate a detailed description of certain phenomena. (Marrow, 2015) as cited by, Altecín, De Leon, Gomez, Grijalvo, Magabo and Villanueva, 2023). In addition, with each step staying close to the data. Transcripts were read repeatedly, significant statement, formulated meaning, cluster themes, developing exhaustive description, producing the fundamental structure and seeking verification of the fundamental structure to extract thematic analysis. As cited by. (Morrow, Roise, Rodriguez, Alison and King, Nigel 2015; Mohamad, 2022; Zaniel, Mohamad & Parcon, 2023; Ugalingan., et al, 2023) The responses of the participants were recorded, noted, and transcribed. The significant statements from the responses of the participants were singled out as basis of getting the code. Mohamad, (2022).

Ethical Considerations

Before allowing this study to take place, the researchers established an ethically sound ambiance. Nothing was done to infringe on the participants' rights to respect, privacy, and protection from physical and psychological damage. The District Supervisor, participants' class adviser, parents/guardians, and participants received the transmittal letters stating that both sides (the researcher and the participant) have agreed to engage in an interview, furthermore, the participants were notified ahead of time that the researcher and the adviser will have access to all of the information acquired. Additionally, the dignity of the subjects of this study were protected in accordance with the "confidentiality clause," which states that no identifying features or information, including names, would be included in transcripts or the final report. Furthermore, deletion of the voice recordings after transcribing was done for safety and confidentiality purposes of the participants of this study. Finally, it was assured that the participants in this study are aware of the study's purpose. The participants in this study were given clear and sufficient background information on which to make their own decisions about whether or not to participate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the phenomenological data gathered to achieve the objective of this study. The data were taken from audio recordings of the in-depth interviews of the Teduray English Language Learners and their English Language teachers. There were twelve (12) target participants in this phenomenological study but only ten (10) have participated. Those were the seven (7) Teduray English Language Learners and three (3) grade 4 English Language teachers from Resa Elementary School, Kinimi Elementary School, and Nalkan Elementary School. These recordings were manually transcribed and translated into English.

Throughout the process of identifying significant statements from each transcript of interviews to formulation of meanings and clustering themes that established the

surfaced patterns, themes were formulated according to influenced factors of the lived experiences of Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning.

The Challenges Encountered by the Grade 4 Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Reading as English Language Parameter

Table 1.1 reflects the significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the responses about the challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in reading as English Language Parameter.

Table 1.1: Challenges Encountered by Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Reading

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	My mama teaches me. I can understand few of it... I can't read other words.	The learner taught by her mother to read.	001	Poor reading comprehension
2	It was Mama..who reads it. I can't read it, I can only read some.	The learner can't read but can read some.	002	Very poor reading
3	I can't read English. Tagalog/Filipino only.	The learner can't read English.	003	Reading problem
4	English is hard ma'am.I can't read it.	The learner can't read.	002	Very poor reading
5	I can only read few from it. I don't understand it. I don't understand the content of our module in English.	The learner can read few but can't understand.	002	Very poor reading comprehension

6	Ahmm.. I can only read few English words ma'am..ahmmm.. It is hard to understand. I understand only few words in English, so I can't answer all of my modules in English.	The learner has difficulty in reading and understanding words in English.	002	Very poor reading comprehension
7	I can read. Ahhmmm... I understand few in English.	The learner can read but cannot understand everything.	002	Very poor reading comprehension

Table 1.1 presents the challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in reading. There were three (3) themes emerged from the seven (7) participants.

Theme 1 “poor reading comprehension” with the code 001, one participant mentioned that he can read some words in English language but there is lack of comprehension on it. This is supported by his statement that: “*My mama teaches me. I can understand few of it... I can't read other words.*” (Transcript 1, lines 40-42)

This implies that Teduary English Language Learners need reinforcement to develop their reading comprehension skill. Reading is beneficial for language acquisition, according to Harmer (2008). Assuming that pupils comprehend what they read, the more they read, the better they get (Setiawan, 2017).

Majority of the participants mentioned that “very poor reading” coded 002 in English language means that it is hard for them to read and comprehend. This made the learners less interested in answering their modules. It was revealed by participant 2 from the transcription quoted as: “*It was Mama..who reads it. I can't read it, I can only read some.*” (Transcript 2, lines 41-43)

Participant 4 mentioned in the interview that she was facing difficulty in reading English language. It was revealed by participant 4 from the transcription and lines: “*English is hard ma'am.I can't read it.*” (Transcript 4, lines 46-47)

Most kids have inadequate reading skills, according to Njie (2013) and Rany (2013), due to a lack of effective learning methodologies, as well as their unwillingness and motivation to learn how to read (Setiawan, 2017).

Theme 3 “reading problem” with the code 003, one participant stated that he was having hard time in answering module since the learner mentioned that he cannot read English words. Participant 3 revealed it from the transcription and lines: *“I can’t read English. Tagalog/Filipino only.”*(Transcription 3, lines 43-44)

According to Njie (2013) and Rany (2013), most pupils have poor reading skills due to a lack of efficient learning methodologies as well as their unwillingness and motivation to learn to read. Setiawan, 2017

Theme 4 “very poor reading comprehension” with the code of 004, three (3) participants denoted that these learners could read but could not comprehend everything they read. The learner found it hard to understand the content of their modules as they revealed. Participant 5 revealed from the transcription and lines: *“I can only read few from it. I don’t understand it. I don’t understand the content of our module in English.”* (Transcript 5, lines 50-55)

When participant 6 was asked about her challenges in reading on Modular Distance Learning, she revealed that she has difficulty in reading and understanding words in English. It was revealed from the transcription and lines: *“Ahmm.. I can only read few English words ma’am..ahmmm.. It is hard to understand. I understand only few words in English, so I can’t answer all of my modules in English.”* (Transcript 6, lines 45-51)

Participant 7 stated on the interview that the learner can read English but cannot understand everything. It was revealed from the transcription and lines: *“I can read. Ahhhmmm... I understand few in English.”* (Transcript 7, lines 55 and 59)

Rany (2013) claims the limitations of pupils’ vocabulary proficiency impedes their reading ability as well as a challenge to teachers when teaching reading strategies to pupils (as cited in Setiawan, 2017).

The Challenges Encountered by the Grade 4 Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Writing as English Language Parameter

Table 1.2 reflects the significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the responses about the challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in writing as English Language Parameter.

Table 1.2: Challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Writing

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	I don't know what to write ma'am.	The learner do not know what to write	101	Very poor in writing
2	I know how to write..but sometimes the spelling is incorrect.	The learner know how to write but poor in spelling	101	Very poor in writing
3	Don't know English Language ma'am.	The learner does not have knowledge on writing using English Language	101	Very poor in writing
4	I know how to write..but I can only write few words.	The learner can write but only few words.	102	Poor writing skill
5	I find it hard to write in English ma'am, but sometimes the answers are found in the module. I'll just rewrite it, I just can't answer some when answers are not found in the module.	The learner finds it hard to write in English language	102	Poor writing skill

6	In English ma'am... spelling is difficult for me.	The learner is having difficulty in spelling.	102	Poor writing skill
7	I rewrite the answers that mama writes.	The learner can write by copying	102	Poor writing skill

Table 1.2 presents challenges encountered by Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in writing. This table emerged two (2) themes from seven (7) participants.

Theme 1 “very poor in writing” with the code 101 showed that the learners struggle on writing using English Language. Participant 1 revealed in the interview that he do not know what to write on his module. He stated it in the lines: *“I don’t know what to write maam.”* (Transcript 1, lines 47-48)

When participant 2 was asked the challenges he encountered on Modular Distance Learning in writing, he responded that he know how to write but poor in spelling. It was stated it from the transcription and lines: *“I know how to write..but sometimes the spelling is incorrect.”* (Transcript 2, lines 57-59)

Participant 3 affirmed on the interview that he does not have knowledge on writing using English Language. It was stated it from the transcription and lines: *“I don’t know English Language ma’am.”* (Transcript 3, lines 49-50)

Students must master particular principles and develop abilities linked to handwriting, spelling, flow, punctuation, and structuring thoughts into readable texts, making writing competency more complicated and harder than other language skills (Richards, Richards, & Renandya & Renandya, 2002; Alsamadani, 2018; Adas & Bakir, 2013, Akhiar, Mydin & Kasuma, 2017). Students' enthusiasm is sometimes stifled by the complexity of writing, which has an impact on their comprehension and performance in language learning. In this regard, Zainab, Isarji, and Zaidi (2017) argued that students with poor writing proficiency tend to perform poorly in written examination and reporting research projects (as cited in Hassan et al., 2021).

Theme 2 “poor writing skill” with the code 102 indicated that the learners do not able to write using English language. As they revealed on the interview, there is lack of interest in answering modules since they struggle on writing using English language. They confirmed it on the transcription and lines: *“I know how to write..but I can only write few words.”* (Transcription 4, lines 56-57); *“I find it hard to write in English ma’am, but*

sometimes the answers are found in the module. I'll just rewrite it, I just can't answer some when answers are not found in the module.” (Transcription 5, lines 64-69); “In English ma’am... spelling is difficult for me.” (Transcription 6, lines 61-62); and “I rewrite the answers that mama writes.” (Transcription 7, lines 65-66)

The primary obstacles identified by Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) were a lack of school funds in the design and delivery of modules, students' struggles with self-study, and parents' lack of understanding to academically assist their child/children. As a result, it is clear that there are issues with using modular distance learning (as cited in Acala and Castroverde, 2021).

The Coping Mechanisms of the Grade 4 Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Reading as English Language Parameter

Table 2.1 reflects the significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the responses about the coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in reading as English Language Parameter.

Table 2.1: Coping Mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Reading

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	I study my lesson ma’am.	The learner do not know what to write	201	Studying the lesson
2	Only Mama answers it.	The learner is dependent on her mother on answering the module.	202	Asking assistance from the mother
3	I ask my older sister to answer it.	The learners asks help from siblings.	203	Asking assistance from the sibling
4	Only my mother answers it.	Learners rely on their parents.	202	Asking assistance from the mother

5	I study my lessons ma'am.	The learner study her lesson.	201	Studying the lesson
6	I ask my older sister to teach me.	The learner asks help from siblings	203	Asking assistance from the sibling
7	She answers it. Mama reads it	The learner becomes dependent due to deficiency of reading.	202	Asking assistance from the mother

Table 2.1 presents coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in reading. The seven (7) participants reveal three (3) themes.

Theme 1 “studying the lesson” with the code 201 revealed that despite the situation facing by the learners during Modular Distance Learning, they express positive attitude towards learning by studying their lessons. It is shown in the transcriptions and lines: “*I study my lesson ma'am.*” (Transcript 1, line 58); “*I study my lessons ma'am.*” (Transcript 5, line 83)

According to Jumat (2014), motivation is vital in boosting students' learning results (as cited in Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). Further, theme 2 “asking assistance from the mother” with the code 202 have shown that some of the Teduray English Language Learners has lack of interest in learning during Modular Distance Learning. The learners ask their parents to answer their modules instead of exerting effort to learn from it. It was revealed from the transcription and lines: “*Only Mama answers it.*” (Transcript 2, lines 72); “*Only my mother answers it.*” (Transcript 4, lines 70-71); and “*She answers it. Mama reads it.*” (Transcript 7, lines 51-52).

Many studies indicate that when parents are involved, children learn and achieve more. Parents should take appropriate care of their children's physical and educational development to the extent that they are able to be independent and satisfy the needs of the world in which they live, according to Ceka and Murati (2016) (as cited in Gevero, 2021).

Theme 3 “asking assistance from the sibling” with the code 203 showed that the learners provide answers to their modules by letting their siblings answer it instead of doing it themselves. This also shows that the learners have less interest in learning the language during Modular Distance Learning since they are having difficulty in reading and comprehension as well. These were revealed on the transcriptions and lines: “*I ask my*

older sister to answer it."(Transcript 3, lines 61-62) and *"I ask my older sister to teach me."* 6 (Transcript 6, lines 76-77).

Nonetheless, all of this is reduced to the point where they are completely aware of their "critical" position as study-buddy in this new usual instruction (Gevero, 2021).

The Coping Mechanisms of the Grade 4 Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Writing as English Language Parameter

Table 2.2 reflects the significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the responses about the coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in writing as English Language Parameter.

Table 2.2: Coping Mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in Writing

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	I call Mama, I ask help from her. I don't know the other topics.	The learner ask help from parent.	301	Asking assistance from the mother
2	Mama writes the asnwrs on a separate paper... then I just transfer it on my module.	The learner rely on their parents on answering their module	301	Asking assistance from the mother
3	My older sister writes answers to my modules.	The learner depends on sibling.	302	Asking assistance from the sibling
4	Only Mama answers it.	The learner depends on parent.	301	Asking assistance from the mother
5	I call my older sister or my papa.	The learner asks help from	302	Asking assistance from

		sibling and parent		the sibling
6	I imitate what my older sister writes.	The learner copies answers given by sibling.	302	Asking assistance from the Sibling
7	I ask Mama to teach me.	The learner asks guide to parent	301	Asking assistance from the mother

In table 2.2, the seven (7) participants reveal four (4) varied answers coded 301, 302, 303, and 304 regarding the coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners in writing on modular Distance Learning.

The first theme “asking assistance from the mother” with the code 301 indicates that due to difficulty in writing using the language, the learners’ best option is to ask help from their parents to answer their modules. Participants 1, 2, 4, and 7 revealed it on the transcriptions and lines: *“I call Mama, I ask help from her. I don’t know the other topics.”* (Transcript 1, lines 68-69); *“Mama writes the answers on a separate paper... then I just transfer it on my module.”* (Transcript 2, lines 82-84); *“Only Mama answers it.”* (Transcript 4, lines 81-82); and *“I ask Mama to teach me.”* (Transcript 7, lines 94)

Gevero (2021) goes on to say that when parents are aware of and involved in their children's educational process, the outcome is more likely to be positive and inspiring. Parents in this survey expressed fears, safety worries, and a sense of duty. Nonetheless, all of this is reduced to the point where they are completely aware of their "critical" position as study-buddy in this new usual instruction (as cited in Matilov, 2002).

Moreover, theme 2 “asking assistance from the sibling” with the code 302 implies that Teduray English Language Learners depend on their sibling when it comes to answering their modules. As they have mentioned on the interview, they find it hard to write using English language. To aid their problem on answering their module, they ask their sibling to provide the answers for them. These was affirmed by the participants 3, 5, and 6 on the transcription and lines: *“My older sister writes answers to my modules.”* (Transcript 3, lines 73-74); *“I call my older sister or my papa.”* (Transcript 5, lines 96-97); and *“I imitate what my older sister writes.”* (Transcript 6, lines 87-88)

Furthermore, reading comprehension teaching styles are vital in the learning process and can influence students' reading comprehension (Tingsona and Aquinob, 2021).

English Language Teachers' Suggested Solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in Reading

The significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the English Language Teachers' suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in reading is shown in the table 3.1

Table 3.1: English Language Teachers' Suggested Solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in Reading

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	As an English teacher, to improve learners' reading skills during Modular Distance Learning, activities that focuses on improving their macro skills such as writing should be lessen while activities that will improve reading skills should be emphasized.	Giving activities that will improve the reading skills of the learners should be focused during Modular Distance Learning.	401	Giving activities that would improve reading skill than writing skill
2	As a teacher, our number one job is to teach learners and to learn from them. In order for the learners to learn well, we have to apply actual learning experience to them and let them reflect on it for their everyday life. I recommend to let the learners read more and comprehend what they are reading. I also suggest to give focus on the slow learners. Giving videos about reading for them to	Reading more and practice comprehension are suggested by the English language teacher Parents' plays important role on learners' learning during Modular Distance	402 403	Practice reading Parents' guidance on the reading activities of their children

	<p>watch might help, but this technique is not easy in this place.</p> <p>Parents also need to guide their children. By giving them extra effort to practice reading in this situation, it can help the learners to excel in their reading skills.</p>	Learning		
3	<p>Learners do not rely on the modules given. I strongly suggest they need extra effort to improve their reading skills like watching television or videos related to the language skills. Let them observe and imitate the unfamiliar words or difficult words and always check the dictionary and ask elders to guide and teach learners.</p>	<p>Integration of the Modular Distance Learning to technology and giving reinforcement to the slow learners were recommended</p>	404	Watching television or videos
		<p>Giving extra effort to the learners is recommended</p>	405	Guidance from the adult learners
		<p>Learners should check unfamiliar words on dictionary.</p>	406	Using dictionary

Table 3.1 presents English Language Teachers' responses on the suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in reading. The three (3) participants revealed six (6) themes.

Theme 1 "giving activities that would improve reading skill than writing skill" with the code 401 reflected that English Language teachers are suggesting that more activities that will focus on the improvement of the reading skill of the learners during Modular Distance Learning. Teacher -participant 1 mentioned it on the transcription below:

“As an English teacher, to improve learners’ reading skills during Modular Distance Learning, activities that focuses on improving their macro skills such as writing should be lessen while activities that will improve reading skills should be emphasized.” (Transcript 1, lines 20-23)

According to a study conducted by Ambayon (2020), modular instruction is more effective in the teaching-learning method than traditional teaching methods since students learn at their own pace in this modular approach (Acala and Castroverde, 2021).

Theme 2 practice reading with the code 402 implied that the English language teacher is aware on the needs of the Teduray English Language Learner during Modular Distance Learning. As he stated on the interview, teachers need to focus on the slow learners and help them read more and practice comprehension for their improvement. Teacher-participant 2 revealed it on the transcription and lines below:

“As a teacher, our number one job is to teach learners and to learn from them. In order for the learners to learn well, we have to apply actual learning experience to them and let them reflect on it for their everyday life. I recommend to let the learners read more and comprehend what they are reading. I also suggest to give focus on the slow learners. Giving videos about reading for them to watch might help, but this technique is not easy in this place. Parents also need to guide their children. By giving them extra effort to practice reading in this situation, it can help the learners to excel in their reading skills.” (Transcript 2, lines 20-30)

It is an unfettered self-learning approach in which pupils are stimulated and their interest is piqued by quick feedback and a comment supplied to practice exercises. As a result, this type of learning modality promotes a student-centered learning strategy. However, instructors, students, and parents faced numerous obstacles as a result of the deployment of modular learning (Acala and Castroverde, 2021).

Theme 3 “parents’ guidance on the reading activities of their children“ with the code 403 emphasized that parents’ plays important role on learners’ knowledge acquisition during Modular Distance Learning. Teacher-participant stated it on the transcription below:

“As a teacher, our number one job is to teach learners and to learn from them. In order for the learners to learn well, we have to apply actual learning experience to them and let them reflect on it for their everyday life. I recommend to let the learners read more and comprehend what they are reading. I also suggest to give focus on the slow learners. Giving videos about reading for them to watch might help, but this technique is not easy in this place. Parents also need to guide their children. By giving them extra effort to practice reading in this situation, it can help the learners to excel in their reading skills.” (Transcript 2, lines 20-30)

Theme 4 “watching television or videos” with the code 404 exposed that integration of the Modular Distance Learning to technology and giving reinforcement to the slow

learners were recommended by the English language teacher as one activity to improve the reading skill of the learner. Teacher-participant 3 stated it on the transcription and lines below:

“Learners do not rely on the modules given. I strongly suggest they need extra effort to improve their reading skills like watching television or videos related to the language skills. Let them observe and imitate the unfamiliar words or difficult words and always check the dictionary and ask elders to guide and teach learners.” (Transcript 3, lines 21-26)

Theme 5 “guidance from the adult learners” with the code 405 exposed that giving extra effort to the learners by guiding them on learning during Modular Distance Learning was suggested by the English language teacher as a help to improve the reading skill of the learners. In addition, guidance from their parents is also essential since parents are the new teachers during this Modular Distance Learning. Teacher-participant 3 stated it on the transcription and lines below:

“Learners do not rely on the modules given. I strongly suggest they need extra effort to improve their reading skills like watching television or videos related to the language skills. Let them observe and imitate the unfamiliar words or difficult words and always check the dictionary and ask elders to guide and teach learners.” (Transcript 3, lines 21-26)

Theme 6 “using dictionary” with the code 406 exposed that learners when they encounter unfamiliar words, they should check it on the dictionary as suggested by the English language teacher as one activity to improve the reading skill of the learners. Teacher-participant 3 detailed it on the transcription and lines below:

“Learners do not rely on the modules given. I strongly suggest they need extra effort to improve their reading skills like watching television or videos related to the language skills. Let them observe and imitate the unfamiliar words or difficult words and always check the dictionary and ask elders to guide and teach learners.” (Transcript 3, lines 21-26)

Moreover, it is undeniable that during this pandemic, learners must realize the importance of the use of other learning materials like checking dictionaries as suggested by the English teacher is necessary.

Other problems for elementary school pupils learning to write include a lack of exposure to books and reading resources, according to Foster (2015). (Jumat, 2014).

English Language Teachers’ Suggested Solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in Writing

The significant statement, formulated meaning, code, and theme clusters of the English Language Teachers’ suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in writing is shown in the table 3.2

Table 3.2: English Language Teachers' Suggested Solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in Writing

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Code	Theme Cluster
1	Activities that will focus on improving writing skill should be easier depending on the level of the learners and to the area they live.	The teacher focus on activities to improve writing skill	501	Giving of simple writing activities
2	For me, writing skills is one of the foundation of the children. To learn from skills, to apply it, but writing skills can be different in its style. The school where I am assigned is very far. Since we are now in the pandemic, we only use Modular Distance Learning. For me, I can suggest to use some videos for the learners to watch. But since it is not easy in this place, tutorial would be a better help. Have a schedule to those pupils who are in need and having problems on their writing skills. When the teacher is free to guide and to enlighten their lack of capacity to write, the learners could manage. Also, parents are the best teacher on guiding their children to learn better.	The teacher helps the learners through tutorial Parents should guide their children to learn better	502 503	Tutorial Parent's guidance

3	Integrate writing in a task in learning materials like rewriting articles in the news. Meaningful activities that enhances writing skills. Writing essay and diaries could encourage them to express their ideas through writing.	Supplementary writing activities will enhance the learners writing skills	504	Giving writing activities
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Table 3.2 presents the English Language Teachers' responses on the suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in writing. The three (3) participants revealed 4 themes.

Theme 1 "giving of simple writing activities" has the code 501 where in the English language teacher suggests that more activities should be given to the learners to improve their writing skill. The teacher should focus on activities that will improve learners' writing skill depending on their capacity. It was implied by teacher-participant 1 on the transcription and lines: "*Activities that will focus on improving writing skill should be easier depending on the level of the learners and to the area they live.*" (Transcript 1, lines 28-30)

Theme 2 "tutorial" have the code 502 which emphasized that the teacher could help the learners through tutorial. He responded during the interview that tutorial would be a better help to the Teduray English Language Learners especially to those who are having problems on their writing skill. It was mentioned by teacher-participant 2 on the transcription and lines below:

"For me, writing skills is one of the foundation of the children. To learn from skills, to apply it, but writing skills can be different in its style. The school where I am assigned is very far. Since we are now in the pandemic, we only use Modular Distance Learning. For me, I can suggest to use some videos for the learners to watch. But since it is not easy in this place, tutorial would be a better help. Have a schedule to those pupils who are in need and having problems on their writing skills. When the teacher is free to guide and to enlighten their lack of capacity to write, the learners could manage. Also, parents are the best teacher on guiding their children to learn better." (Transcript 2, lines 34-46)

Theme 3 "parent's guidance" have the code 503 stressed that parents should guide their children to learn better. Consequently, guidance of the parents on learners' education has big impact to their learning. It was stated by teacher-participant 2 on the transcription and lines below:

“For me, writing skills is one of the foundation of the children. To learn from skills, to apply it, but writing skills can be different in its style. The school where I am assigned is very far. Since we are now in the pandemic, we only use Modular Distance Learning. For me, I can suggest to use some videos for the learners to watch. But since it is not easy in this place, tutorial would be a better help. Have a schedule to those pupils who are in need and having problems on their writing skills. When the teacher is free to guide and to enlighten their lack of capacity to write, the learners could manage. Also, parents are the best teacher on guiding their children to learn better.” (Transcript 2, lines 34-46)

Theme 4 “giving writing activities” have the code 504 stressed that supplementary writing activities will enhance the learners writing skills. More writing activities like writing essay and diaries as mentioned in the interview, would help the learners improve their writing skill and could encourage them to express their ideas. It was implied by teacher-participant 3 on the transcription and lines: *“Integrate writing in a task in learning materials like rewriting articles in the news. Meaningful activities that enhances writing skills. Writing essay and diaries could encourage them to express their ideas through writing.”* (Transcript 3, lines 30-33)

"Many writing problems may stem from too little time dedicated to writing instruction or from writing instruction improperly designed around the learning needs of many students," according to Stein, Dixon, and Isaacson (1994) (as cited by Defazio et al., 2010)

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

Based on the data gathered and presented, the following are the findings of the study:

1. The challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in reading are poor reading comprehension, very poor reading, reading problem, and very poor reading comprehension.
2. The challenges encountered by the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in writing are very poor in writing and poor writing skill.
3. The coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in writing are studying the lesson, asking assistance from the mother, and asking assistance from the sibling.
4. The coping mechanisms of the Teduray English Language Learners on Modular Distance Learning in writing are asking assistance from the mother, and asking assistance from the sibling.

5. The English Language Teachers' responses on the suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in reading are giving activities that will improve reading skill, practice reading, parents' guidance on the reading activities of the children, using dictionary, and guidance from adult learners.

6. The English Language Teachers' responses on the suggested solutions for the Teduray English Language Learner on Modular Distance Learning in writing are giving of simple writing activities, tutorial, parent's guidance, and giving writing activities.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the results, it is concluded that Teduray English Language Learners have encountered serious challenges both in reading comprehension and writing comprehension. Furthermore, most learners have cope these challenges by depending on their parents or sibling in answering their modules.

However, their English Language teachers suggested that giving more activities to improve the reading and writing skills of the learners would be a great help. Moreover, giving extra effort on tutorial to the learners especially to the slow learners is also suggested.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are recommended.

1. The Department of Education may deploy additional English teachers that will enhance the reading and writing skills of the pupils.
2. The school administration may conduct seminar or training to capacitate English teachers to plan and implement remedial reading and writing program in school.
3. The English language teachers may develop strategies to address the learners' weaknesses in reading and writing skills in Modular Distance Learning.
4. The English Language Learners may develop genuine love for reading and writing to complete their reading and writing tasks in their modules.
5. The English teachers may use interesting reading and writing materials like Big Books and Guided Writing to enhance pupils' reading and writing skills.
6. Other researchers may conduct similar study to other setting and participants to further validate the result of the study. .

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Since the study is qualitative in nature particularly phenomenology. The research studies involved District Supervisor, English Teachers, class advisers, and parents/guardians, were received the transmittal letters stating that both sides (the researcher and the participant) have agreed to engage in an in-depth interview in order to explicate the significant statement needed to the study. the participants were notified ahead of time that the researchers and the adviser will have access to all of the information acquired. Additionally, the dignity of the subjects of this study were protected in accordance with the "confidentiality clause," which states that no identifying features or information, including names, would be included in transcripts or the final report.

Furthermore, deletion of the voice recordings after transcribing was done for safety and confidentiality purposes of the participants of this study.

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